

Original Research

The Role of Marketing Mix on Voluntary Tax Compliance: Small Taxpayers' Experience in Dodoma City

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Abstract

Importance of 4Cs of marketing mix on voluntary tax compliance has been acknowledged. However, contrary to its importance, the body of literature has paid little attention regarding 4Cs of marketing mix in relation to the voluntary tax compliance. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to analyse the influence of the 4 Cs of marketing mix on voluntary tax compliance among small taxpayers. This study applied explanatory cross-sectional survey design to collect and analyse both quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data were collected from small business managers/owners who were selected using systematic random sampling technique, while qualitative data were collected from three TRA officers selected purposively. The quantitative data was gathered using structured questionnaire from 240 managers/owners of small businesses in Dodoma City. The quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics and binary logistic regression model, while qualitative data were analysed using content analysis. The findings of this study indicate that, satisfaction of customer needs and wants, convenience of tax compliance and communication between TRA and tax-payers have positive and significant association with voluntary tax compliance. However, cost of tax compliance has negative and significant effect on voluntary tax compliance. The findings of the study bring knowledge contribution by adding in the body of empirical literature on tax compliance the effect of 4Cs of marketing mix on the voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers. Based on findings this study recommends to TRA to review tax compliance procedures and documentations so as to identify all unnecessary to be removed.

Keywords: Marketing Mix, Tax-payer, Voluntary Tax Compliance, 4Ps.

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Introduction

Taxes are one of the essential elements in management of national income, which consist of estimation of national revenues and expenditures. Also, taxes play a key role in social developments (Kessy, 2020). Governments are using taxes as essential tool to control the economy, encourage investment, regulate inflation, and re-distribute riches and income in society (Mwerera, 2019). Thus, for the governments to be able to effectively manage their activities they have to collect more taxes regardless of the difficulties associated (Nguyen, 2022). The tax revenue collection is an essential aspect of government finance since it provides a steady source of revenue that is used to fund public services and investments (Omary & Pastory, 2022). Thus, tax revenue collection is critical in ensuring the government has the necessary funds to finance its budget and provide essential services to citizens (Dom et al., 2022). Tax compliance is a critical factor for effective tax collection (Chindengwike, 2022; Kassa, 2021; Omary & Pastory, 2022).

According to Chindengwike (2021a), tax compliance is the readiness of taxpayer to obey the tax policy of the country of residence, such as filing of tax returns appropriately, declaring returns and paying all the taxes on a timely basis. For more efficient and effective tax system, tax payers must feel indebted to their government and pay the owed tax of their own free will or voluntarily. The voluntary tax compliance refers to the accurate, complete, and on time payment of taxes without the need for forced efforts by the tax administrators (Kirchler & Wahl, 2010). Voluntary tax compliance strengthens tax management by reducing cost incurred by tax administration authority to enforce tax compliance, increases government tax revenue collection, and allows taxpayers to avoid penalties and disturbances from tax administrators, (Chindengwike & Kira, 2022; Hamisi, 2017). Voluntary tax compliance can improve tax administrators' communication and engagement with taxpayers by providing required information about tax obligations, tax reforms and amendments, and simplify tax processes and procedures (Okello, 2014).

Recognizing this, the government of United Republic of Tanzania implemented various measures to improve tax collection system by improving taxpayer's voluntary tax compliance through among other increasing the number of employees of Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) and revenue collectors in Local Government Authorities [LGAs] (Kessy, 2020). Moreover, the government implemented Electronic Fiscal Devices (EFDs) with the aim to simplify declaration and filling of tax returns in order to encourage voluntary tax compliance among taxpayers (Lyimo & Makilully, 2022). The aim was to induce convenience and simplification of filling tax returns since EFD ensures filling of tax returns online that can be done by taxpayers wherever they are and whenever they want without going to TRA offices (Ngailo, 2022).

Lubua (2014) identified other efforts including enforcement of Income Tax Act (ITA), utilization of Income Taxation System (ITAX) and Custom Application Online System (CULAS). Moreover, TRA empowered the taxpayers' education department by increasing its budget so that it can effectively disseminate education to more taxpayers (B H P Mwakabungu, 2016). At first these efforts led to a 7.5% increase in revenue collection between the 2015/2016 and 2017/2018 financial years (National Audit Office of Tanzania, 2020). Then revenue collection fell from 17% in 2015/16 to 11.1% in

2021/22 (National Audit Office, 2020). Though some studies have noted that TRA is making good progress in terms of revenue collection (URT-MoF, 2021), most studies indicate the presence of many tax payers who do not file their tax returns with the authority (Malima, 2019), low level of voluntary tax compliance as many taxpayers are coerced to comply with their tax obligations (Chindengwike & Kira, 2022). This trend suggests that the voluntary tax compliance among taxpayers was not achieved as planned.

Essentially, to achieve voluntary tax compliance taxpayers must have positive attitude and perception toward tax and tax system (Çevik & Yeniçeri, 2013; Hartner et al., 2010). Therefore, understanding of taxpayers' attitude and perception towards tax and tax system is crucial in improving the voluntary tax compliance rate. Tax laws, rules and regulations are coercive measures, which only result in temporary tax compliance for fear of being punished as tax law requires (Bătrâncea et al., 2012). Thus, the taxpayers perceive tax system as being cruel and punitive; and thus taxpayers behave arrogantly toward tax and tax regime; they comply only lest being fined but not patriotically (Namaliya, 2017). Thus, to acquire taxpayers' loyalty must be the endeavour of TRA so that to have taxpayers who are willing to comply. Since the relationship between TRA and taxpayers is that of service provider and client or customer, therefore, marketing principles can be used to gain loyalty of taxpayers, and thus improve the voluntary tax compliance. Marketing mix is set of marketing instruments that companies utilises to pursue loyalty of its customers in the identified market (Potgieter & Naidoo, 2017).

The marketing mix historically positioned around the 4Ps; product, price, place and promotion (Idris, 2021; Singh, 2012). The 4Ps focus on market, competitors and business (Fei et al., 2021). However, in the 1990s, the model of 4 Cs was introduced as a more customer-driven replacement of the 4 Ps (Lauterborn, 1990; Msuya et al., 2020). The 4 Cs focuses on what customer perceive regarding their needs, situation, experience and satisfaction (Akbar et al., 2022; Lauterborn, 1990). The 4 Cs are important because success of any organization depend on the satisfaction of clients or customer (Fei et al., 2021). Moreover, according to Cheng (2017), the 4 Cs are better applied in company that offer a service and non-technical products, because selling a service depend on customer experience while product sell for its technical specification (Babaei et al., 2017).

Research identify two models based on 4Cs, namely Lauterborn's 4Cs which comprises of consumer or customer wants and needs, cost, convenience and communication (Lauterborn, 1990); and Shimizu's 4Cs that comprises of commodity, cost, channel and communication (Babaei et al., 2017). However, Lauterborn (1990) model is a more consumer-orientated version of the 4 Ps (Fei et al., 2021). The customer wants and needs refer to taxpayers' needs and wants. Understand customers' needs and wants is a first and most pertinent step in marketing since can ensure company offer the right services (Adhiambo, 2019). However, to ensure maximum effect, tax compliance cost which considers the expenses incurred by taxpayers in the process of filling tax returns and making tax payments have to be affordable and minimal. Chindengwike (2021a) posit that higher tax compliance cost has negative impact on voluntary tax compliance, and reduces tax revenue collection. The TRA can improve taxpayers' voluntary compliance by putting in place the system that reduces tax compliance cost that incurred by taxpayers.

Moreover, the taxpayers' convenience of filling tax returns and tax payments takes into account the simplicity of tax return filling procedures and tax payment. Thus, the administrative structure in its simplified ways can improve the convenience of tax collection for eligible taxpayers (Kirchler & Wahl, 2010; Potgieter & Naidoo, 2017). In the era of internet, introduction of electronic systems such as EFDs have been used to reduce compliance costs and promote convenience among taxpayers (Ngailo, 2022). Researches (Chambi, 2020; Lyimo & Makilully, 2022) have acknowledged that EFDs have reduced compliance costs and increased convenience of taxpayers to file for tax returns and tax payments. Furthermore, communication is cooperation between the company and clients with the aim of creating a dialogue regarding their needs. So, how the TRA communicate effectively with eligible taxpayers to educate them on tax laws and regulations, and the importance of compliance is important for increasing positive attitudes for voluntary tax compliance (Hamisi, 2017).

However, contrary to its importance, the body of literature has paid little attention to the concept of 4Cs of marketing mix especially in relation to the voluntary tax compliance. Many studies have reported that voluntary tax compliance is low in Tanzania (E Hassan et al., 2021), but these studies have not linked 4Cs of marketing mix and voluntary tax compliance at the taxpayers' perspectives. This is because, most research in Tanzania have focused on the company's perspectives (Lubua, 2014; Mbufu, 2013). Therefore the proposed study aims at analysing the influence of the 4 Cs of marketing mix on voluntary tax compliance among taxpayers.

This paper is organized as follows: following the introduction part, a second part is a literature review with theoretical and empirical studies that shed a light on linkage between theory and practice in marketing and tax compliance. The third part describes research methods and data analysis techniques utilized in this paper. Thereafter, follows findings, implications and discussions. Finally, based on the findings this paper provides conclusions, recommendations, future research directions and limitations.

Literature Review

This section covers theoretical foundation of this study and review of relevant empirical studies. Its aim is to establish a link between the hypotheses and empirical reviews.

Theoretical framework

Equity Theory

Equity theory is a social psychology concept that suggests that individuals strive to maintain a sense of fairness in their social relationships. The major concept linking Equity theory and tax compliance is through the concept of distributive justice (Roberts & Roberts, 2020). Distributive justice refers to the perceived fairness of how rewards and benefits are distributed within a society (Abbas, 2016). In the context of taxation, distributive justice might be evaluated based on whether the tax burden is distributed fairly across different income levels and socioeconomic groups. For example, if taxpayers perceive that the tax system is unfair, then they may be less likely to comply with tax laws

or more likely to engage in tax evasion (E Hassan et al., 2021). Another way that equity theory might be applied to tax compliance is through the concept of procedural justice. Procedural justice refers to the perceived fairness of the procedures used to make decisions and allocate resources (Farrar, 2015). In the context of taxation, procedural justice might be evaluated based on the convenience of the tax system through communication, the cost of complying with tax laws, and the perceived responsiveness of tax authorities to taxpayer concerns. Taxpayers who perceive the tax system to be procedurally fair may be more likely to comply with tax laws, while those who perceive the system to be unfair may be less likely to comply. Therefore, equity theory provides a useful framework for understanding influence of 4 Cs of marketing mix on voluntary tax compliance. However, theoretical foundation of Equity Theory paints little attention to the concept of the 4 Cs of marketing mix in relation to the voluntary tax compliance. Thus, the 4 Cs marketing mix model was adopted.

The 4Cs Marketing Mix Model

The 4C's marketing mix is one of the most impactful marketing strategies (Idris, 2021). The 4Cs of marketing mix is a business tool which was developed by R.F. Lauterborn in 1990. According to Akbar et al., (2022), the model is a consumer focus and comprises the 4Cs as in Customer wants, cost, convenience and communication. The customer is the company's focus rather than the product. According to Cheng (2017), in order to provide high value, companies have to focus on the needs and wants of the customers. Moreover, the cost component determines how much payment a consumer is willing and able to recompense in exchange for satisfaction (Babaei et al., 2017). When viewed through the eyes of the consumer, the price becomes the cost. Therefore, the first question the management of the company has to ask itself is how much price consumer is willing to pay for the service. In addition, convenience implies carefully positioning the goods at several sales sites, customers and consumers should have easy access to the ease with which marketers provide their products. Lastly but not least, through communication marketers convey the value they provide to clients (Fei et al., 2021). Cheng, (2017) iterated that 4Cs of marketing mix is designed to understand the real needs of customers. In relation to voluntary tax compliance, the theory is relevant to this study as it addresses the application of the marketing mix model into operational activities of TRA as tax collections authority.

Empirical Literature Review

Influence of customer needs and wants on voluntary tax compliances

Customers are the primary emphasis in accomplishing organizational objectives, and they must be prioritized (Tusiime, 2019). Understanding the customer wants is one of the most effective marketing strategies that companies engage in. The sensitivity of the customers has been demonstrated in a report by Fei *et al.*, (2021) whereas the customers wishes and requirements are guidance in service provision. Akbar et al., (2020) established that the most significant task of the company is to follow consumer wants and needs for services and also to shape desired purchasing behavior. A high level of customer satisfaction is argued to lead to stronger company image, reputation of the company, protection of market share, increased customer loyalty, decreased customer complaints

and strengthened company performance (Fei et al., 2021; Jarad, 2020), and induce voluntary tax compliance (Adhiambo, 2019; Hamisi, 2017). Understanding the needs and desires of taxpayers may entice them to comply with collections voluntarily (Akbar et al., 2022). Therefore, in order persuade tax payers comply with voluntary payments, the tax collection authority should understand their needs and wants. Based on the reviewed studies the research may suggest a hypothesis about the consumer:

H₁: There is no positive and significant relationship between customer needs and voluntary tax compliance.

Cost and voluntary compliances

The cost is the sum charged for the consumption of products or services (Odhiambo, 2015). It is the entirety of all the values that a customer foregoes in return for the benefits of owning or using a product or service (Chowdhury & Naheed, 2022). Cost may cover finance, time, and other resources in acquiring services to meet consumer wants and needs (Akbar et al., 2020). Cost reflection in any products and services must be affordable, and the products and services provided must be equal to their value (Idris, 2021). Işoraité (2016) argued that “cost is perceived as the only element of the marketing mix, generating revenue and the most important customer satisfaction and loyalty factor”. Furthermore, Ellitan (2023) emphasizes that customers usually compare the value obtained by acquiring the delivered product or service. If able to make the customers feel that the product and service are higher than the cost, the customer will make a purchase (Chowdhury & Naheed, 2022). The cost function in this study is concerned with the tax paid by tax payers, incurred expenses to comply with tax system, time and energy used for tax compliance, confidence and loyalty of the tax payers to the authorities concerned with revenue collections and utilization (Chindengwike, 2022). Taxpayers’ voluntary compliance considers the trust and confidence towards the tax collection process and their utilization as cost (Bett, 2020; Tilahun, 2019). So, the study hypothesizes that:

H₂: There is no positive and significant relationship between cost incurred by tax payers and voluntary tax compliance.

Convenience and voluntary compliances

Convenience is a quality of ease or accessibility, it refers to the ease with which customers can obtain the goods and services they want (Cheng, 2017). The quality of services should meet the expectation of customers, nothing less than what the customer has promised to provide (Jarad, 2020). Convenience according to Akbar et al., (2020), is the course of attaining the desired products or services through physical or online distribution channels. Convenience can be further explained as how easy it is for the user to change or adopt new behavior and how easy to access any relevant support from certain provided service as argued by Jarad, (2020). For the case in point, fast service, freedom of information on revenue collections, responsible corporate behavior, transparency for accountability such as disclosure to improve public services and targets self-governing citizens such as individual customers/beneficiaries as well as regulatory transparency (Kosack & Fung, 2014). Moreover, Nuseir and Madanat (2015) highlight the practice of

creating all possible environments to maintain positive attitudes on customers so that they may feel as part of business. So, based on the reviewed literature it is hypothesized that;

H₃: There is no positive and significant relationship between convenience and voluntary tax compliance.

Communication and voluntary compliances

Commenting on communication, Nuseir and Madanat (2015) argues that is the marketing strategy, which includes advertising, public relations, personal selling, and sales promotion with the aim of spreading information about service provided. Moreover, Idris (2021) and Akbar et al. (2020) highlights on communication with consumers into two sides whereas one-way communication aiming to inform the target audience about the characteristics of products or services using various communication platforms and the two-way communication in some cases with the aim of helping users to adopt the desired behavior and tackle issues which may come across as barriers in the behavior change process. Thus, communication with customers using the appropriate strategies can help a marketing campaign succeed (Idris, 2021). Alshrideh, Shaltoni and Hijawi (2014) suggested that companies have to use well-informed messages, education and awareness campaigns to pursued customers. In relation to the voluntary tax compliances, communication means the use of different suitable strategies and channels to persuade taxpayers' compliances (Hamisi, 2017; Bett, 2020). Thus, education and mass campaign programs for tax payers and potential tax payers are necessary in order to induce a sense of voluntary tax compliance (Aondo, 2018; Adhiambo, 2019). In addition, positive relationship with tax payers, getting opinion and feedback from tax payers during revenue collections process have to be considered seriously (Bett, 2020). Therefore, based on the reviewed literature it is hypothesized that;

H₄: There is no positive and significant relationship between communication and voluntary tax compliance.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 depicts the conceptual framework that outlines the link between the independent variable, which are 4Cs of marketing mix, and dependent variable 'voluntary tax compliance'. Regarding customer needs Shiferaw and Tesfaye (2020) posit that understanding taxpayer' needs and wants are important for improvement of voluntary tax compliance. The 4Cs model suggests that when convenience increases induces a positive effect on the voluntary tax compliance (AONDO, 2018). Additionally, cost incurred by taxpayers during the process of complying with tax laws and regulations have positive effect on voluntary tax compliance in case the incurred cost are lower compared to what taxpayer had anticipated (Chindengwike, 2022). Moreover, communications between tax authorities and tax payers have significant (Nguyen, 2022).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Methods and Tools

Study area

The study was conducted in Dodoma City of Tanzania. This City was selected as the research location due to the recent growth of business ventures due to increase of number of people in the in the area since the government of URT shifted its headquarters from Dar es Salaam to Dodoma City (Msuya, Moshi & Levira, 2020). Besides, Chindengwike (2022a) reported the presence of tax non-compliance among taxpayers in the Dodoma City. Despite the challenges related to poor tax compliance is wide spread across the country, Dodoma was chosen as the study location due to the abundance of taxpayers and newly established businesses (African Development Bank Group and Urban and Municipal Development Fund, 2021).

Type of research approach and design

In this study both qualitative and quantitative methods were used to complement each other through triangulation and enhance the credibility of the study outcomes (Saunders, 2009; Creswell, 2014) . Thus, explanatory cross-sectional survey design was applied in order to blend quantitative and qualitative methods. The study is explanatory study because examined and described the relationship between the 4Cs of marketing mix and voluntary tax compliance. Though both time series and cross-sectional design can be applied to assess the effect of 4Cs of marketing mix on voluntary tax compliance, for the purpose of this study the cross-sectional design was applied. The foremost reason is that

the cross-sectional was used in this study because it involved collecting data from multiple variables at a single point in time (Saunders, 2009), which included; customer needs and wants, cost, convenience, communication and voluntary tax compliance. On the contrary, time series design only capable of focussing on one variable over time. Also, despite the fact that time series data allow for examination of changes in taxpayer behaviour over time, however the purpose of this study was to gauge the status of voluntary tax compliance in relation to 4Cs of marketing mix. This dictated the use of cross-sectional design. Moreover, use of cross-sectional design offered several advantages to this study, namely greater control over the study variables during data collection, which minimized potential errors and biases (Kothari, 2004). In addition, the design enabled researcher to identify possible prediction relationship between 4Cs of marketing mix and voluntary tax compliance. In Furthermore, the incorporation of survey design enabled the researcher to gather a large amount of information in a relatively short period of time (Saunders, 2009). Lastly but not least, the combination of cross-sectional and survey research designs allowed for generalisation of findings to small taxpayers in Dodoma region, and paint a good picture of voluntary tax compliance with respect to 4Cs of marketing mix among small taxpayers in Tanzania (Hair et al., 2017).

Target population and sampling method

The study population was all taxpayers in Tanzania, while the targeted population is all small taxpayers in Dodoma City. These are small firms. In the firms unit of enquiry is owner/manager of business. These individuals are targeted because they have relevant information to the research topic, which is to examine their perceptions towards the 4Cs of marketing mix applied by the TRA. Also, they are the ones who are directly impacted by the marketing mix strategies and tax compliance policies implemented by the TRA. Their perceptions towards voluntary tax compliance are most important information needed in this study. The systematic random sampling method was applied to select taxpayers from an up-to-date list of registered taxpayers available at TRA Dodoma region office. On the contrary, key informants were selected using purposive sampling technique. In this study three TRA officers at Dodoma City Tax office in the department of taxpayers' education, tax collection and tax enforcement unit were interviewed.

Sample size

The sample size for this study was determined based on statistical considerations and took into account the size of the population, the level of variability in the population, and the desired level of precision for the research results. Researchers (Bougie & Sekaran, 2019) have provided various recommendations for sample size. Sekaran (2003) suggested that a sample size of 30 can be considered a minimum, while 100 is considered a fair sample size, 150-200 good sample, 300-400 very good and 500 is considered an excellent sample size. Aaker et al. (2004) suggested that for logistic regression a sample size of 150-200 is considered good, and provide reliable findings that can be generalized to population. Besides, recent studies on tax compliance among Dodoma taxpayers have employed sample sizes ranging from 100 to 200 (Eliamini, 2018). Based on these scientific facts, the sample size for this study was 180 taxpayers.

Data Collection

On one hand, survey method was used to capture primary quantitative data of which semi structured questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection with both closed and open-ended questions. This helped to collect data related to respondents' demographic characteristic using variables like age, gender, education, experience, type of business, business age; customer satisfaction, cost of compliance, convenience of tax compliance procedures and effectiveness or level of communication between TRA and taxpayers. The questions were measured using the 5-point Likert scale which allowed the researcher to cover a wider geographical area using less time and cost (Krishnaswami & Ranganatham, 2010). On the other hand, in-depth interview was used to gather qualitative data from TRA officers. This method gathered information on taxpayers' needs and wants, tax compliance cost, convenience of complying with tax and communication between tax administrators and taxpayers. In-depth interview was used because it is flexible and allows researcher to gather first hand information from respondents. In addition, Secondary data were collected from the academic publications and from reports and bulletins of Tanzania Revenue Authority, Ministry of Finance (MoF) and Bank of Tanzania (BoT). A checklist or kit listing the required data will be prepared to guide data collection and ensure only relevant data are collected.

Data Analysis

Qualitative data were analysed using thematic analysis. Subsequent to data gathering, the data were transcribed from the interview notes/audio and field documents. The data were typed and saved in Microsoft word format. The anchors codes were created for each research question and labels assigned to them. Then, the researcher prepared a matrix form with list of codes and group the codes based on participants' responses and record number of their occurrences. Then a researcher created the themes of the highly mentioned codes. Then the results were used to explain quantitative results for every variable. In case of quantitative data, both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. Basic descriptive statistics in terms of percentages were used to describe the sample and the characteristics of the respondents. The inferential statistics based on chi-square, Kendall's tau-b correlation coefficient and binary logistic regression model was applied to examine the link between 4Cs of marketing mix and voluntary tax compliance. The binary logistic regression model was applied since tax compliance is a binary variable with two responses; 1= voluntary tax compliance and 0= if non-voluntary tax compliance. The general multiple logistic binary regression model is given as:

$$\text{logit}[\pi(x)] = \log\left(\frac{\pi(x)}{1-\pi(x)}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_p x_p \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Whereby, $\pi(x)$ represent the likelihood of voluntary tax compliance, x_i 's represent set of independent variables and β_i 's represent parameters of respective independent variables.

Variables of correlational and logistic binary regression analysis

The dependent variable for this study is voluntary tax compliance measured using binary responses was coded as '1' = voluntary tax compliance, '0' = non-voluntary tax compliance. On other hand, the independent variables were 4Cs of marketing mix, namely, satisfaction of customer needs and wants, cost of compliance, convenience of compliance and communication between TRA and taxpayers. The independent variables were measured categorically using five point Likert scale (1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= neither Disagree no Agree, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly Agree). The variable customer needs and wants had two items. To reduce the voluminous amount of data, the scale variable measured in two levels was created. To create this variable, the mean scores of the two items of customer needs and wants were computed. In addition to that an overall mean score of all the two items was also computed. Then, scores of the two items were then grouped into two categories, the first category included items with average scores less than overall mean and the second category included all subjects with average scores greater than overall mean. The first category was regarded to disagree to voluntarily comply with tax and coded '1', whereas the second was regarded to agree to comply with tax voluntarily' and was coded '2'. The same procedure was conducted for cost of compliance, convenience and communication.

Assumptions of logistic regression model

Before running data in logistic regression model, assumptions relating to this model were tested and found to be acceptable.

➤ Firstly, the dependent variable must have binary responses or a dichotomy variable. This study's dependent variable obeys this assumption. The dependent variable 'voluntary tax compliance' was measured by binary responses '1' = voluntary tax compliance, '0' if non-voluntary tax compliance

➤ Secondly, the model assumes that the independent variables are continuous and categorical (multi and binomial). Independent variables in this study are in five-point Likert scales, which is categorical type.

➤ Thirdly, theoretically, the model should be fitted correctly. Neither over fitting nor under fitting should occur. Therefore, the model goodness of fit tests was calculated. On one hand the model was statistically significant (χ^2 (3, N=379) = 63.017, p= 0.000). This means the data regarding the 4Cs of marketing mix fits to the estimated model. On the other hand, the goodness of fit of the model was assessed using Hosmer and Lemeshow Goodness-of-Fit Test and the results (χ^2 (4, N=180) = 2.339, p= 0.749), show that our logistic regression model fit well to the data.

Reliability

The results show that, the overall Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient of satisfaction of customer wants and needs is 0.84, cost is 0.76, convenience is 7.89 and communication is 0.86. According to Cronbach (1951), the coefficients indicate that, data collection

instruments were reliable and so as the collected data. As such, the 4Cc of marketing mix is good measure of voluntary tax compliance among taxpayers in Dodoma City.

Findings and Discussions

Demographic Features of Respondents

The results in Table 1 indicate that, 46.0% (n=180) of surveyed small tax-payers were males and 54.0% (n=177) were females. This tells us that, most of the small tax-payers are females. The finding is in line with Chirwa (2008), Mori (2014), Zampetakis, Bakatsaki, Kafetsios and Moustakis (2016) and Chhabra and Karmarkar (2018) who posit that most of small entrepreneurs are women. Nevertheless, the findings of this study show that the difference between male and female is not significant (54%-46%=8%). In this study it was important to be aware of sex distribution among small tax-payers since equal gender representation is among the worlds' agendas in social, economic and political activities. Moreover, results in Table 1 show that the majority of the surveyed small tax-payers have 48-57 years of age. They comprised 32.0% (n=57) of all respondents. Moreover, those who have 38-47 years and 28-37 years were 31.0% (n=56) and 23.0% (n=37) in that order. The lower end comprised those with 20-29 years of age and more than 60 years of age who were 12.0% and 4.0% respectively. The findings of this study are in line with the study conducted by Kanoni (2015) and Mrindoko (2022). It also gives an indication of the level of maturity and awareness of tax-payers regarding the importance of voluntary tax compliance to business operations.

Table 1. Distribution of Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n=180)

Variable/parameter	Measurement	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	83	46.00
	Female	97	54.00
Age	18-27 Years	11	6.00
	28-37 Years	41	23.00
	38-47 Years	56	31.00
	48-57 Years	57	32.00
	58+	15	8.00
Business experience	<1 Year	20	11.00
	1-5 Years	27	15.00
	6-10 Years	68	38.00
	11+ Years	65	36.00
Education level	Primary	43	24.00
	Secondary	65	36.00
	Certificate/Diploma	34	19.00
	Bachelor	22	12.00
	Masters	14	8.00
	PhD	2	1.00

Furthermore, results in Table 1 show that small tax-payers who have 6-10 years' experience in business comprised 38.0% (n=68), and were the majority followed by those

who have more than 11 years experience who were 36.0% (n=65). Moreover, those with 1-5 years experience were 15.0% (n=27), and the lowest were those with less than one year of experience. Therefore, majority of small tax payers had considerable experience in business management. Therefore, this study implies that years of experience in business management has provided the surveyed small tax-payers knowledge to understand the importance of voluntary tax compliance for the business operations. In addition, results in Table 1 indicate that 36.0% (n=65) and 24.0% (n=43) of surveyed small tax-payers had secondary and primary education respectively. Besides, the results show that 19.0% (n=34) and 12.0% (n=22) of surveyed small tax payers posses Diploma and Bachelor degree correspondingly. Lowest end comprise small tax-payers with Masters Degree (8.0%, n=14) and PhD (1.0%, n=2). The results imply that most of small tax-payers are regarded as knowledgeable to be able to provide this study with relevant answers.

Correlation between ICT competence and use of e-recruitment portal

Results in Table 2 shows that satisfaction of customer needs and wants by revenue collection authorities such as TRA has a significant relationship ($\chi^2(4, N=180) = 22.827, p=.000$) with voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers, and the link based on Kendall's tau b correlation coefficient is positive and strong ($\tau_b=.327, \rho=.001$). This signifies that, customer satisfaction is an indispensable predictor of voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers. Similar results that show strong, positive and significant relationship was observed for convenience ($\chi^2(4, N=180) = 49.489, p=.000; \tau_b=.394, \rho=.000$). This result implies that convenience in compliance procedures and documentation enhances voluntary tax compliance. In addition, the findings in Table 2 show that communication between revenue collection authority and tax-payers has significant relationship with voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers ($\chi^2(4, N=180) = 70.356, p=.000$). The Kendall's tau b correlation coefficient also shows significant association between communication and voluntary tax compliance, and the association is positive and strong ($\tau_b=.338, \rho=.000$). This means that effective communication between TRA and small tax-payers is essential determinant of the tax-payers' voluntary compliance to tax payment and other tax-related submissions.

Table 2. Correlation of Marketing Mix and Voluntary Tax Compliance (n=180)

Variables	Chi square-value	Chi square ρ value	df	Kendall's tau b Value	Kendall's tau b p value
Satisfaction of customer needs and wants	22.827	0.000	4	0.327	0.001
Tax compliance cost	49.489	0.000	4	0.394	0.000
Convenience of compliance	70.356	0.000	4	0.338	0.000
Communication	56.462	0.000	3	0.382	0.000
Overall Marketing Mix	46.577	0.000	1	0.366	0.000

Furthermore, Table 2 indicate that transaction cost associated with tax compliance procedures has significant relationship $\chi^2(3, N=180) = 56.462, p=.000$ with voluntary

tax compliance among small tax-payers. However, Kendall's tau b coefficient of correlation depict a negative and strong association between transaction cost for tax compliance and voluntary tax compliance, which was statistically significant ($\tau_b = -.382$, $\rho = .000$). This means that compliance cost is an important predictor of voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers. Generally, the findings in Table 2 show that, overall correlation of marketing mix is highly significant ($\chi^2(1, N=180) = 46.577$, $p = .000$) with voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers. The Kendall's' tau b correlation coefficient also shows high significant association between marketing mix and voluntary tax compliance. The association is positive and strong ($\tau_b = .366$, $\rho = .000$). This result entail that application of marketing mix by TRA in tax collection make tax-payers fill obliged to pay their taxes, and hence increases voluntary tax compliance. So, the 4Cs of marketing mix are very crucial determinants of voluntary tax compliance in Tanzania.

Moreover, a binary logistic regression was performed to estimate the association of 4Cs of Marketing mix and voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers. Findings in Table 3 indicate that the overall logistic regression model was statistically significant, ($\chi^2(3, N = 180) = 60.318$, $p = .000$). The model explained 16.2% (Cox and Snell R^2) to 29.0% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in voluntary tax compliance, and correctly classified 85.8% of responses given by small tax-payers. The Cox & Snell R Square and Nagelkerke R Square, are referred to as pseudo R-squared and are both methods of calculating the explained prediction power of independent variables on dependent variable (Nagelkerke, 1991). They measure the extent of variation of the dependent variable caused by independent variables. In this model the -2 Log Likelihood statistics is 292.914, which is far from zero, and thus, a model fits well at predicting the association between 4Cs of marketing mix and voluntary tax compliance. The -2 Log Likelihood measures how poorly the model predicts the decisions and the smaller the statistic the better the model (Cox, 1975; Nagelkerke, 1991). In addition, Hosmer-Lemeshow test ($\chi^2(4, N=180) = 2.339$, $p = 0.749$), which means goodness of fit of a model is attained and thus data predicts well the association of 4Cs of marketing mix and voluntary tax compliance.

Table 3. Results based on Logistic Binary Regression Model (N=180)

Variable(s)	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Customer needs and wants(1)	3.244	.773	16.080	1	.000	21.064	5.221	92.997
Tax compliance cost(1)	-2.362	.474	24.791	1	.000	.094	.037	.239
Compliance convenience(1)	2.164	.633	11.696	1	.001	8.709	2.519	30.107
Communication(1)	1.080	.403	7.125	1	.007	2.944	1.334	6.497
Constant	1.701	.469	13.159	1	.000	5.480		

Regarding the relationship between satisfaction of customer needs and wants and voluntary tax compliance (Table 3), it was found that small tax-payers who agreed to that TRA has satisfied their needs and wants were significantly ($p = 0.000$) twenty one times more likely to report that they voluntarily comply with tax requirements compare to those who their needs and wants were not satisfied with TRA (OR=21.064, 95% CI [5.221, 92.997]). Moreover, the logistic regression coefficient is positive ($\beta = 3.244$) implying that

as satisfaction of customer needs and wants increases; the voluntary tax compliance also increases. This means that a unit increase in satisfaction of customer needs and wants is associated with an increase of voluntary tax compliance by 3.244 units. The standard error (SE) of estimate reveals a small chance 0.773 that the estimate could be wrong, and Wald test value (16.080) is very large than SE to ensure the significant relationship between predictor and outcome variables.

Therefore, the hypotheses H_1 : *There is no positive and significant relationship between customer needs and voluntary tax compliance* was rejected. The plausible explanation is that, satisfaction of customer needs and wants by TRA increases the tax-payers awareness and self obligation to pay tax, which enhances voluntary compliance to tax. The findings are in line with theoretical thinking of equity theory and the 4Cs marketing mix model, which identifies customer satisfaction, compliance cost, compliance convenience and communication with clients to enable effective tax administration to ensure voluntary tax compliance among tax-payers. The findings are in line with Babaei *et al.* (2017), Fei *et al.* (2021) and Jarad (2020) who iterated that, in order persuade tax payers comply with voluntary payments tax administration authorities such as TRA in Tanzania are to first determine customers' needs and wants so as to serve them better. The aim is to make sure that taxpayers are satisfied with the services TRA offer so that to entice them to pay with restraint.

Essentially, economies where the provision of tax compliance services is satisfactory, the tax evasion rates are low. However, tax-payers can honestly feel justified in evading taxes if they feel that the quality and quantity of services offered by tax administration authority is unsatisfactory. Thus, according to Hamisi (2017), understanding customers' needs and wants is a first and most pertinent step in marketing since can ensure company offer the right services, and also, assist a company to devise strategies to communicate what it offers. Theoretically, higher customer satisfaction has been confirmed to express good customer loyalty, decreased customer complaints, increased market penetration and market share, higher sales volume, good business image and stronger and sustainable profitability (Fei *et al.*, 2021; Jarad, 2020). For tax administration authorities, customer satisfaction increases trust of tax-payers and thus readiness of tax-payers to pay their due balance, which induces voluntary tax compliance. Tax payers will tend to comply with their tax obligation if they feel that their tax administration authority is honest, transparent and participatory.

Furthermore, Table 3 show results regarding the relationship between cost of tax compliance and voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers. It was found that small tax-payers who agreed that the cost of tax compliance is low were significantly ($p=0.000$) less likely to report that they voluntarily complied to their tax obligations compare to those who said that the cost of tax compliance is high and unaffordable (OR=0.094, 95% CI [0.037, 0.239]). Moreover, the logistic regression coefficient is negative ($\beta=-2.362$) implying that as cost of tax compliance increases, the voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers decreases. This means that a unit increase in cost of tax compliance is associated with a decrease of voluntary tax compliance by 2.362 units. The standard error (SE) of estimate reveals a small chance 0.474 that the estimate could be wrong, and Wald test value (24.791) is very large than SE to ensure the significant relationship between predictor and outcome variables.

Therefore, the study failed to reject hypotheses H_2 : *There is no positive and significant relationship between cost incurred by tax payers and voluntary tax compliance*. The plausible explanation is that, higher costs of tax compliance among small tax-payers decreases voluntary compliance to tax obligation thereby making tax-payers dislike paying tax. As such the government loses revenue through tax aversion and avoidance. Also, during the in-depth interview with TRA officers this study was informed that most small tax-payers own small to medium business, which has a lot of challenges including capital that restrict their profitability and growth as well as sustainability. As such, for them to survive they must make sure that they operate at lower costs. So, most of these businesses are cost sensitive, and that is reason they opt to avoid tax as a surviving strategy. The findings are similar to Chindengwike (2021a) who reported that higher tax compliance cost has negative impact on voluntary tax compliance, and reduces tax revenue collection.

Practically, cost of tax compliance among small tax-payers are higher due to among others the lack of financial knowledge and skills. They depend on outsourcing financial analysts to prepare for them tax return documents and financial statements that are required by tax administration authorities. According to ACTIONAID Tanzania (2016), tax system of Tanzania is said to follow a progressive route, but is not progressive enough to make high-profit makers in the economy to pay more taxes than low-income earners such as small business owners. Thus, to attain a fair tax system is essential, since it will make higher earners pay more so as to encourage lower earners to willingly pay their tax obligations. Theoretically, tax-payers who perceive the tax system to be procedurally fair are expected to comply with tax laws than those who perceive the system to be unfair may be less likely to comply and engage in unethical procedures such as tax avoidance, forgery of tax documents and tax aversion. The tax-payers as other customers compare the value obtained by paying tax voluntarily and the cost incurred in the process of paying tax. Thus, when a tax-payer feel that the benefits of paying tax are higher than the cost, they voluntarily pay their tax obligations.

Additionally, Table 3 show results regarding the relationship between compliance convenience and voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers, it was found that small tax-payers who agreed that TRA has offered tax compliance convenience were approximately nine times more likely to report that they voluntarily comply with their tax obligations compare to those who disagreed that the TRA has provided them with convenience in complying with their tax obligations (OR=8.709, 95% CI [2.519, 30.107]). The relationship is significant ($p=0.001$). Moreover, the logistic regression coefficient is positive ($\beta=2.164$) implying that as convenience increases, also the voluntary tax compliance increases. This means that a unit increase in convenience of tax compliance is associated with an increase of voluntary tax compliance by 2.164 units. The standard error (SE) of estimate reveals a small chance 0.633 that the estimate could be wrong, and Wald test value (11.696) is very large than SE to ensure the significant relationship between predictor and outcome variables.

Therefore, the hypotheses H_3 : *There is no positive and significant relationship between convenience of tax compliance and voluntary tax compliance* was rejected. The plausible explanation is that, convenience of tax compliance increases voluntary tax compliance. The findings are in line with theoretical thinking of equity theory and 4Cs marketing mix

model. The findings corroborate with Nuseir and Madanat (2015), Jarad (2020), Akbar et al. (2020) and Idris (2021). Besides, Adhiambo (2019) found that improvement in tax system and procedures increases convenience of tax payment which in turn increases voluntary tax compliance. Provision of all necessary requirements that assist client to easily fulfill their tax obligations may enhance tax-payers satisfaction and hence voluntary tax compliance. The 4Cs model suggests that when convenience increases induces a positive effect on the voluntary tax compliance (Aondo, 2018). In the current era of technological advancement such as use of information and communication technologies has enabled convenient ways of tax payment and collection whereby tax-payers need not to go to TRA offices. Payments and filling of necessary documents can be done via internet using Electronic Fiscal Devices (EFDs) and computers. These have reduced compliance costs and enhanced compliance convenience among tax-payers (Ngailo, 2022; Lyimo & Makilully, 2022).

Regarding the relationship between communication between TRA and tax-payers and voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers, the findings in Table 3 indicate that tax-payers who agreed that TRA has been in constant communication with tax-payers were significantly ($p=0.007$) three times more likely to report that they voluntarily comply to tax system compare to those who disagreed ($OR=2.944$, 95% CI [1.334, 6.497]). Moreover, the logistic regression coefficient is positive ($\beta=1.080$) implying that as communication between TRA and tax-payers increases voluntary tax compliance. This means that a unit increases in communication between TRA and tax-payers is associated with an increase of voluntary tax compliance by 1.080 units. The standard error (SE) of estimate reveals a small chance 0.403 that the estimate could be wrong, and Wald test value (7.125) is very large than SE to ensure the significant relationship between predictor and outcome variables.

Therefore, the hypotheses H_4 : *There is no positive and significant relationship between communication and voluntary tax compliance* was rejected. The plausible explanation is that, communication between TRA and tax-payers increases influences tax-payers behavior toward voluntary tax compliance and reduces the intention for tax avoidance and aversion, and hence increases the government revenue collection. The findings conforms to the 4Cs marketing mix model, which state that organizations must communicate with clients to convey message regarding the products or services offered by the organization as well as the benefits and utility expected to be derived from those products. Communication can be via education, advertisement and promotional campaigns or seminars as well as using fliers and stickers. According to Adhiambo (2019), revenue authorities have to communicate effectively with eligible taxpayers regarding to tax laws and regulations. Tax-payers must be told of the efforts made to simplify the tax collection process to increase trust and cooperation with tax-payers, and promote voluntary compliance.

Conclusion and Implications

Conclusion

Based on the finding, this study concludes that, satisfaction of small tax-payers' needs and wants leads to voluntary tax compliance through an improved services and simplified

tax compliance procedures. The improvement in quality of tax compliance services such as internet and documentation process encourage tax-payers to comply with their tax obligations through reduced cost of compliance and increased tax-payers convenience. Also, this study concludes that small tax-payers are cost sensitive and thus an increase in cost of tax compliance reduces voluntary tax compliance, and thus encourages tax avoidance and aversion among small tax-payers. Moreover, this study concludes that communication among TRA and tax-payers enhances voluntary compliance to tax obligation among small tax-payers. Besides, this study acknowledges that, though tax compliance has cost implication to small businesses profitability, their benefits are far more important for the nation.

Implications of the Study

The findings of the study bring knowledge contribution by adding in the body of empirical literature on tax compliance the effect of 4Cs of marketing mix on the voluntary tax compliance among small tax-payers. Based on the findings and theoretical underpinning of equity theory, policymakers can design tax systems that are perceived as relatively fair and just, which can improve voluntary tax compliance and reduce tax evasion and avoidance among small tax-payers. In turn, this increases government revenue collection.

Study recommendations

Satisfaction of customer wants and needs is one of the most effective marketing strategies that organisations engage in order to attain customer loyalty. Based on the findings it is recommended to the TRA to determine first the needs and wants of tax-payers and other stakeholders before formulating tax collection by-laws and regulations through a participatory dialogue on order to enhance collection of tax, which is the main purpose of the tax system. Moreover, TRA should enhance its communication channel with tax-payers as a strategy for enhancing mutual relationship between TRA and tax payers through the provision of all necessary information required by tax-payers. In addition, based on findings this study recommend to TRA to review tax compliance procedures and documentations so as to identify all unnecessary steps that can be removed or combined to reduce lengthy and complications that add cost to tax-payers.

Study limitations and Suggestion for Future Studies

This study has several unavoidable limitations. The first and foremost is the fact that this study focused on voluntary tax compliance among small taxpayers located in Dodoma City alone whilst the small taxpayers are all over the country. Thus, future study have to consider widening the study area to cover more than one region or city. This is envisaged to provide a better representation and generalizability of the results to the whole small taxpayers' population. Moreover, the scope of this study was limited to voluntary tax compliance and 4Cs of marketing mix that based on customer features. There are factors not included in the 4Cs marketing mix model that could also influence voluntary tax compliance. They include 4Ps of marketing mix that are based on product/service features; and demographic features of firms and their managers/owners. Thus, the present study can be broadened further by focusing on the 4Ps of marketing mix of services

offered by TRA to taxpayers. Moreover, firm's features and their managers/owners such as age, sex, knowledge, skills, education level, business experience, firm size, business type, level of formality and ownership are important variables that can be considered into future studies. The aim is to understand the impact of these variables on voluntary tax compliance. It is necessary to understand this in order to see if there is need to formulate discriminatory regulations based on these features.

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References

- Abbas, M. (2016). *Inter-nation tax equity: An enquiry into the distributive justice concerns of international tax allocations between countries*. Queen's University.
- Adhiambo, O. J. (2019). *Factors affecting tax compliance among small scale traders in Nakuru Town, Kenya*. Unpublished MBA Project, Kenyatta University.
- Akbar, M. B., Lawson, A., & Turner, N. (2022). Lauterborn's 4Cs. In *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of Social Marketing* (pp. 1–8). Springer.
- AONDO, R. (2018). *Factors Affecting Tax Compliance Among Small And Medium Enterprises (SMEs) In Nakuru County In Kenya: A Survey Of SMEs In Naivasha Sub County*. MUA.
- B H P Mwakabungu. (2016). *Effect Of Taxpayer Education On Voluntary Tax Compliance By Value Added Tax (Vat) Taxpayers In Dodoma, Tanzania*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29519.97446>
- Babaei, M. R., Mostakhtemi, R., & Esmaili, S. (2017). Identifying the effect of marketing mix 4C's on customers satisfaction of life insurance (Case study: Pasargad insurance offices in Tehran). *Agricultural Marketing and Commercialization Journal*, 1(1), 43–53.
- BĂTRÂNCEA, L. M., Nichita, R. A., Bătrâncea, I., & Moldovan, B. A. (2012). Tax compliance models: From economic to behavioral approaches. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 8(36), 13–26.
- Bett, M. C. (2020). *Factors Affecting Tax Compliance by Small and Medium Enterprises in Sotik Sub-County in Bomet County in Kenya*. United States International University-Africa.
- Bougie, R., & Sekaran, U. (2019). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.

- Çevik, S., & Yeniçeri, H. (2013). The relationship between social norms and tax compliance: The moderating role of the effectiveness of tax administration. *International Journal of Economic Sciences*, 2013(3).
- Chambi, G. (2020). An Assessment of Effectiveness of Electronic Fiscal Devices (EFDS) in Enhancing Revenue Collection for the Government of Tanzania: A Case Study of Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) In Dar es Salaam City.
- Cheng, T. (2017). Research on Marketing Strategy of Electronic Components. 4th International Conference on Education, Management, Arts, Economics and Social Science (ICEMAESS 2017), 236–240.
- Chindengwike, J. (2022). The effect of tax compliance cost on taxpayer's voluntary compliance in Tanzania. Available at SSRN 4115252.
- Chindengwike, J., & Kira, A. R. (2022). The Effect of Tax Rate on Taxpayers' Voluntary Compliance in Tanzania. *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 10(5), 889–896.
- Chowdhury, T. A., & Naheed, S. (2022). Multidimensional political marketing mix model for developing countries: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Political Marketing*, 21(1), 56–84.
- Dom, R., Custers, A., Davenport, S., & Prichard, W. (2022). Innovations in Tax Compliance: Building Trust, Navigating Politics, and Tailoring Reform. *The World Bank*. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-1755-7>
- E Hassan, I., Naeem, A., & Gulzar, S. (2021). Voluntary tax compliance behavior of individual taxpayers in Pakistan. *Financial Innovation*, 7(1), 21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-021-00234-4>
- Farrar, J. (2015). An empirical analysis of taxpayers fairness preferences from Canadas Taxpayer Bill of rights. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 7(5), 71–79.
- Fei, W., Zhang, Z., & Deng, Q. (2021). Universal Pictures' SWOT Analysis and 4Ps & 4Cs Marketing Strategies in the Post-COVID-19 Era: 2021 International Conference on Public Relations and Social Sciences (ICPRSS 2021), Kunming, China. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.211020.205>
- Hair, J. F., Celsi, M. W., Ortinau, D. J., & Bush, R. P. (2017). *Essentials of marketing research*. McGraw-Hill.
- Hamisi, S. (2017). Factors influencing tax compliance among SMEs in Dar-es-salaam. University of Dodoma.
- Hartner, M., Kirchler, E., Poshalko, A., & Rechberge, S. (2010). Taxpayers' compliance by procedural and interactional fairness perceptions and social identity. *Journal of Psychology & Economics*, 3(1), 12–31.

- Idris, J. (2021). Marketing mix 4Cs: Impact on small and medium Entrepreneurs (SMEs) marketing performance. *Proceeding of the 8th International Conference on Management and Muamalah*, 221–226.
- Jarad, G. (2020). Application of the 4Cs marketing mix in the digital environment. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(10), 2113–2122.
- Kassa, E. T. (2021). Factors influencing taxpayers to engage in tax evasion: Evidence from Woldia City administration micro, small, and large enterprise taxpayers. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 10(1), 8.
- Kessy, S. S. (2020). Electronic payment and revenue collection in local government authorities in Tanzania: Evidence from Kinondoni municipality. *Tanzanian Economic Review*, 9(2).
- Kirchler, E., & Wahl, I. (2010). Tax compliance inventory TAX-I: Designing an inventory for surveys of tax compliance. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 31(3), 331–346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2010.01.002>
- Kosack, S., & Fung, A. (2014). Does Transparency Improve Governance? *Annual Review of Political Science*, 17(1), 65–87. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-032210-144356>
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.
- Lauterborn, B. (1990). New marketing litany: Four Ps passé: C-words take over.
- Lubua, E. W. (2014). Influencing tax compliance in SMEs through the use of ICTs. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 2(1), 80–90.
- Lyimo, B. J., & Makilully, M. H. (2022). Impact of electronic fiscal devices towards revenue collection in Tanzania. *Olva Academy*, 4(1), 97–100.
- Malima, M. (2019). *Factors Influencing Voluntary Tax Compliance in SMES Based in Kinondoni Tax Region*. Mzumbe University.
- Mbufu, A. K. (2013). *The impact of revenue collection on service Delivery in local governments: A case study of Ilala municipal council*. Mzumbe University.
- Msuya, I., Moshi, I., & Levira, F. (2020). Dodoma: Building a sustainable city to meet neighbourhood needs. *SHLC Research Summary*, 12.
- Mwerera, G. M. (2019). *Factors affecting tax compliance among small and medium enterprises in Embakasi East region, Nairobi, Kenya*.
- Namaliya, N. G. (2017). *Strategies for maximizing revenue collection in public water utility companies*. Walden University.

- Ngailo, S. M. (2022). The Effectiveness of Electronic Fiscal Devices on Enhancing Tax Compliance in Tanzania. The Open University of Tanzania.
- Nguyen, T. H. (2022). The Impact of Non-Economic Factors on Voluntary Tax Compliance Behavior: A Case Study of Small and Medium Enterprises in Vietnam. *Economies*, 10(8), 179. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies10080179>
- Odhiambo, V. A. (2015). Effects of marketing strategies on the performance of retail stores in footwear sector in Nairobi City County. University of Nairobi.
- Okello, A. (2014). Managing Income Tax Compliance through Self-Assessment. IMF Working Papers, 14(41), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781475515237.001>
- Omary, E., & Pastory, D. (2022). Determinants of Tax Compliance among Small and Medium Enterprises in Tanzania: Insights from Ilala Municipality.
- Potgieter, L. M., & Naidoo, R. (2017). Factors explaining user loyalty in a social media-based brand community. *SA Journal of Information Management*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajim.v19i1.744>
- Roberts, M. L., & Roberts, T. L. (2020). Distributive Justice and the Tax Fairness Partisan Divide. In *Advances in taxation* (pp. 73–99). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Singh, M. (2012). Marketing mix of 4P's for competitive advantage. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 3(6), 40–45.
- Tilahun, M. (2019). Economic and Social Factors of Voluntary Tax Compliance: Evidence from Bahir Dar City. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 06(02). <https://doi.org/10.35248/2472-114X.18.6.182>
- Tusiime, J. (2019). Effect of packaging on the sales volume of an organization. Kampala International University, College of Economics and Management.

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